

Australian Government

Department of Climate Change, Energy,
the Environment and Water

Annual Livestock Emissions Reduction Forum held on 13 August 2024

Project Summaries

Methane Emissions Reduction in Livestock (MERiL) 1 & 2

LESGAF000043_Radio-frequency identification (RFID) to assess and refine delivery systems for anti-methanogenic additives

Department of Primary Industries and Regional Development (NSW)

Introduction

Delivering anti-methanogenic additives to sheep through low-volume (e.g., coarse salt) and high-volume (e.g., pellets) supplements requires consistent daily intake, which is rarely achieved in extensive grazing systems. RFID systems provide a potential solution by monitoring the time sheep spend at feeders and their visitation patterns, aiding management for more uniform supplement consumption.

The aims of the present project were:

a) Feasibility and validation: a1) assess the detection accuracy of low-frequency (LF) and ultra-high-frequency (UHF) RFID systems on loose-lick and lick feeders; a2) provide recommendations for optimising RFID performance in on-farm scenarios.

b) Field studies: b1) evaluate the effectiveness of LF and UHF RFID in monitoring sheep attendance and time spent at feeders over time and individually; b2) investigate the potential effectiveness of 'lick feeders' for higher-volume (pellets/grain) and 'loose-lick feeders' for lower-volume (salt) in delivering anti-methanogenic additives with Agolin® Ruminant as a model.

Feasibility and validation

Tag exposure testing was performed at various power levels, panel heights, and distances from the panel face for loose and lick feeders. Both LF and UHF RFID systems effectively tracked tag appearance and duration. LF detected tags reliably up to 15 cm from the panel face at 12V, with reduced reliability beyond this range. UHF achieved higher tag detection at 240 dBm, but with weaker signals and potential false positives. Intermediate power settings (e.g., 220 dBm) are advised for UHF to balance accuracy with minimal errors. Camera footage validation confirmed a high correlation between RFID-recorded time and observed sheep presence. Enhancing feeder designs in tandem with RFID systems, such as optimizing antenna and reader panel placement, and reliable software for automatic data processing, autonomous solar powering with easy data retrieval is crucial for broader adoption.

Field studies

A total of 360 crossbred lambs were adapted to the diet and technology before being allocated to a four-week study across two sites: Cowra, using loose-lick feeders with salt, and Wagga Wagga, using lick feeders with pellets. The study involved two RFID systems (LF and UHF), with each replicate consisting of 45 lambs grazing in a paddock. Pellets contained 0.2 mg/kg of Agolin, while for salt, it was sprayed on.

Results indicated that the LF and UHF RFID systems led to similar conclusions when monitoring time spent and visitation frequency across different supplement types. Our findings reveal significant variability in sheep attendance and potentially inconsistent methanogenic additive consumption, using salt and pellets as additive carriers.

Figure 1 illustrates the number of days individual lambs (i.e. single dot) achieved a specific time target at the loose-lick feeders. On average, lambs spent 2.47 min/an/day; however, this target was met only on 14 out of 28 days (50%) by 16% of the animals (15 out of 90 lambs). Table 1 similarly indicates that individual lambs met the flock's average time on 2.53 consecutive days out of 7 (36%). Weekly average time spent at the loose-lick feeders was 1.6, 1.7, 3.8, and 2.7 min/an/day for weeks 1 through 4, respectively.

Figure 1: Box plots for the number of days individual animals spent, using a loose-lick feeder equipped with low frequency (LF) RFID systems, above four baseline statistical measures (min/an/day), First quartile (Q1) = 0.40, median = 1.3, mean = 2.47 and third quartile (Q3) = 3.

Table 1: Average number of consecutive days per week that individual animals spent at feeders using a low-frequency RFID system, above four baseline statistical measures (min/an/day), First quartile (Q1) = 0.40, median = 1.3, mean = 2.47 and third quartile (Q3) = 3.

Week number	Q1	Median	Mean	Q3
Low frequency				
Week 1	3.13	1.75	1.07	0.90
Week 2	3.94	2.07	1.10	0.82
Week 3	4.53	3.30	2.53	2.25
Week 4	4.78	2.75	1.73	1.38

Each bar in Figure 2 represents an individual lamb consuming pellets from a lick feeder equipped with LF or UHF RFID systems. The average time spent by lambs, as recorded by LF (bottom right plot), was 28.4 min/an/day, ranging from 0.7 to 113.8 minutes. Notably, 26 lambs (~30%) spent less than 10 min/day at the feeders, likely not meeting the required intake of anti-methanogenic additives. The plots show a moderate to high correlation between time spent and visits, with more frequent visits relative to time spent for some animals. Analysing this association over time for each lamb yielded an R² above 0.90, suggesting attendance can serve as a reliable proxy for time spent, simplifying monitoring.

Figure 2: Average metrics for individual lambs consuming pellets delivered using lick feeders with low-frequency (right) and ultra-high frequency (left) RFID systems. The top plot shows the average daily gain (g/an/day), the middle plot shows the average number of events (an/day), and the bottom plot shows the average daily time spent per day per animal (min/an/day). Error bars indicate SEM for each metric.

Take-home message

LF and UHF RFID systems on feeders are valuable for monitoring sheep attendance and time spent. However, further optimisation is needed, as current evidence suggests that uniformity in additive consumption may not be achieved over time or at the individual level for a significant proportion of the sheep. Software and data retrieval enhancements could boost performance and adoption.